

**THE CONCEPT OF SPIRITUALITY AND ENLIGHTENMENT, THEIR
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Abstract: In the current developing era, each nation has its own history and spirituality, and they preserve and honor these shrines. Our Uzbek people have their own rich history and high spirituality. In our country there are great people who sacrificed their lives for the sake of education, who worked hard to make the people literate. These days these people and concepts are losing their meaning, but a person without history is like a corpse. In the next article you will learn about these concepts.

Key words: Enlightenment, society, person, education, people, spirit, history, maturity.

Spirituality, spirituality and enlightenment, the correct definition of the correlation and correlation of enlightenment are important in the education of spiritually mature and perfect people, in the spiritual and educational development of society. Any society has its own spiritual needs, among which the leading place is occupied by the need for knowledge. Because a physically and mentally healthy person constantly strives to learn. Spirituality always develops in harmony with enlightenment, that is, with knowledge. Only if we can achieve harmony of both, we can ensure that our youth are raised as morally perfect, religious, patriotic, humane, conscientious, pious, noble, honest and pure people. bu Hamid Muhammad Ghazali expressed the following thoughts on this matter: Misguided people think that “when they have knowledge, there is no need to apply it. Such thoughts are the beliefs of those who are content with knowledge and deny Sharia, and for them there is knowledge, but no action. They do not know that such knowledge is useless. However, the punishment for a person who does not follow the knowledge he has received will be double on the Day of Judgment. Acquiring knowledge and knowledge and applying it in everyday practical activities leads to the strengthening of many spiritual qualities such as honesty, faith, conscience, sincerity. “Spirituality is an incomparable force that calls a person to spiritual purification, spiritual growth, the inner world of a person, strengthening his will, completing his faith, awakening his conscience, which is the criterion of all his views.”I. A. Karimov. Only people with high spirituality and enlightenment live like my people, my country and consider it happiness to be kind to others, help those in need and show them the right path. People with high spirituality and wisdom ease the hardships of the suffering,

share their sorrows, ease their pain, and take care of orphans. People who have this quality have a highly developed sense of national pride, national pride and patriotism. They consider it an honor to defend the honor of their people and the interests of their people. When the independence of the Motherland is under threat, they spare their lives and property, and show examples of dedication and heroism in the name of its defense. Based on the above, it is incorrect to conclude that only enlightened people will have high spirituality. If we look at the history of mankind, not all spiritual people have always been enlightened. At the same time, we see that not all knowledgeable and enlightened people are highly spiritual. In relation to such people, our people rightly used the wise saying: "There was a scientist, but he was not a man," expressing a deep meaning. In other words, there are people who are not scientists. He may not be a scientist, but he is highly spiritual. There are scientists unworthy of humanity. It's complicated. There is no benefit from them to the country. As our people have learned, there is no rice without rice. This expression was used only in relation to certain intellectuals, whose spirituality is rare in life. People looked at such people with hatred. On the contrary, those who studied with people of knowledge who harmoniously embodied spirituality and enlightenment wanted their children to grow up to be such people. Along with the above phrase, our people also used the phrase "Don't be a scientist, be a man." This situation does not mean that spirituality and enlightenment negate each other. On the contrary, spirituality and enlightenment are mutually harmonious, closely related, mutually reinforcing factors that lead a person and society to perfection. As our President said, no matter what period of our history we took, we saw that the desire for science, education and high spirituality in our country never stopped, as an immortal symbol of the genius of our people, this was clearly manifested even in the most difficult and complex times. We can achieve Our ancestors from ancient times considered knowledge, education and upbringing to be priceless wealth, the most basic condition and guarantee of human improvement and development of the nation.⁸¹ There were scientists who embodied spirituality and enlightenment at a high level. They lit the fires of spirituality and enlightenment like torches. Spirituality and enlightenment are necessary, like water and air, for the bright future of our people, nation and Motherland. Mutual unity and harmony of spirituality and education, joint implementation of spiritual and educational work is the key to our progress. They cannot be separated from each other. As the Head of our state stated: "... the main goal and task in the field of education is to raise our children into perfect people who have the ability to think independently and broadly, and to live consciously. For this, it is necessary that

educational work be carried out harmoniously, because “the path to a person’s heart begins first of all with education.”

Only by ensuring their true harmony will it be possible to educate a perfect personality, ensure the independence and high development of our Motherland. The technical knowledge of our youth and the ability to master complex technologies must be combined with spiritual maturity and independent thinking. Mental intelligence and spiritual potential are the two wings of our spiritual and enlightened youth. The President emphasized the tasks in this regard and said: “any nation and nation striving to find its place in the current complex and cruel era must thoroughly and comprehensively comprehend the achievements of universal development... Our great enlightened grandfather Mahmudhoja Behbudi said at the beginning of the last century: in the secular world. No wonder he called on the Turkestan people to awaken the consciousness of the Turkestan people with truthful thoughts that “science and knowledge are necessary, a nation without modern science and science will be trampled.” on others”. time is also proven.”

It is important that we never forget the hadith that says: “Do not forget this world for the sake of this world and the next world for the sake of the Hereafter” in approaching the issue of spirituality and enlightenment. Since history and life experience, worldly and religious values, knowledge and enlightenment have always complemented and enriched each other, this indicates that on this basis people have reached the heights of spiritual maturity. With spiritual and educational poverty, no nation or country in which it lives will ever be able to reach the highest heights of economic, social and political development. Spirituality and enlightenment. At the beginning of the 20th century, the famous Russian orientalist Oldenburg said that the spiritual achievements of Europe are still at the level of an infant compared to the heights of maturity that Eastern spirituality reached in the past. Why now? In my opinion, this conclusion should have been formed on the basis of admiration for the perfect methods of enlightenment, means and methods of spiritual education, consciously developed in the process of centuries-old spiritual development of the East¹. Enlightenment is knowledge and science, which in the sense of acquisition, is a concept reflecting the degree of acquisition of knowledge and sciences about nature, society, human nature and aspects related to it. Education is carried out through the education system. Education is a tool and means of spreading enlightenment among people. It includes educational institutions such as pre-school educational institutions, secondary educational institutions, academic lyceums and vocational colleges. Higher educational institutions operating in our country also play an important role in disseminating education among students and youth. Enlightenment eliminates addiction, fear and hadid, giving man

incomparable divine power and unprecedented potential. The people of our country have strived for enlightenment since time immemorial. That is why thinkers and scientists came from this country and made a great contribution to the development of science for all mankind. Ferghani, Khorezmi, Farabi, Ibn Sina, Ulugbek, Bukhari, Termizi, Margilani, Motrudi, Zamakhshari and others not only reached the heights of knowledge, but also widely propagated it - that is, enlightenment, those who taught, those who educated students. The Turkestan educational school has a rich past and great heritage. Mahmudhoja Behbudi, Munavvar Kari Abdurashidkhan son, Ashurali Zahiri, Saidrasul Saidazizi, Ishak Khan Ibrat, Ahmad Donish and others believed that enlightenment is the only way to liberate the country and people from national oppression and educational backwardness. The enlightened scientist Abdullah Awlani wrote: "Knowledge is the honor of the world and the honor of the hereafter." Knowledge is a very high and sacred quality for a person. Because knowledge shows us our situation and actions like a mirror. It sharpens our mind and thoughts like a sword. A person without knowledge is like a tree without fruit." The English philosopher F. Bacon said: "Knowledge is power, and power is in knowledge," and Rudakiy explained that knowledge is important in a person's life, saying: "Knowledge is a shield in spite of all difficulties." President Islam Karimov put forward the conceptual idea "Strength is in knowledge and thinking" and emphasized that knowledge is the power that makes a person's spirituality holistic, helps him overcome any difficulties, fight evil and alien ideas. Summarizing the views of our great ancestors on the mutual harmony of education and upbringing, our President stated: "Education cannot be separated from education, and education cannot be separated from education - this is an eastern view, an eastern philosophy of life"³. . Education is of paramount importance in shaping a person's personality. It includes the educational process, all educational activities. Only when any education is combined with upbringing does it become the basis of mature spirituality, raising a spiritually mature and perfect person.

Summary We can say that every country has its own spirituality, and this spirituality lifts it to heights. Therefore, in our country it is necessary to educate children in the spirit of spirituality from preschool education. This spirituality of ours goes back several years. , so it is appropriate to pay attention to families. To increase enlightenment, we need to acquire more knowledge, people who read books are certainly enlightened.

References:

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